

ACTIVE Second Campaign Log

Events

Second Campaign	
14-Jan	Monsoon has set in. Showers all around and northwesterly flow. Monsoon trough south of us.
15-Jan	Monsoon intensifying
16-Jan	Dornier moved from hangar. 2 days needed to pump AMS
17-Jan	Despite extremely wet morning, Egrett makes it in in the much quieter afternoon. Data system worked OK, lidar didn't
18-Jan	Planned Do flight postponed because power supply failure caused loss of vacuum on AMS. Meeting with TWP-ICE Pis in the evening
19-Jan	Official opening and press day up to 11.00. Do test flight TD13 in the afternoon, round Tiwis. Egrett cloud physics payload installed
20-Jan	First mission, AD14/AE17, to investigate squall line progressing N over Tiwis. Do measured along its length to the N, Egrett to the S
21-Jan	Down day to get into synch with TWPICE.
22-Jan	Joint flight AD015/AE18/Twin Otter looking at storm south of Darwin. Successful flight, only problem was with AMS.
23-Jan	Joint flight AE19/Twin Otter looking at dissipating anvil over the Timor Sea. Successful
24-Jan	No flight today because of uninterrupted rain caused by squall line/MCS overnight
25-Jan	All five aircraft flew today: we did SD16/AE20; Egrett did aged Ci anvil and Dornier survey mission round Tiwis
26-Jan	Survey flight SD17 to the south of Darwin, curtailed because of turbulence
27-Jan	Four aircraft today: Egrett (AE21)/Proteus/TO looked at aged Ci anvil; Dornier (SD18) completed survey mission to the S
28-Jan	Down day as Egrett is converted to ozone lidar flights
29-Jan	Down day as AMS is repaired on Dornier. TWP-ICE plan yet another aged anvil mission.
30-Jan	Dornier flight SD19 to measure chemical equator. No Egrett flight due to aileron problem
31-Jan	First Egrett lidar flight (LE22), curtailed because lidar didn't work. Planned Alice Springs flight. Ozonesonde problems.
01-Feb	Dornier flew to Alice Springs (SD20). Egrett lidar flight LE23 in evening - mission completed despite failure of lidar
02-Feb	Dornier back from Alice Springs (SD21). Egrett switched to cloud physics payload. Proteus/TO fly in anvils over Tiwis
03-Feb	Both aircraft do survey missions to the north: SD22 and SE24
04-Feb	Deep dry layer prevented significant convection today.
05-Feb	Down day again
06-Feb	Joint flight with Proteus and TO into detached Hector anvil north and west of Melville Is. Do circulated storm at 1000 and 2000'
07-Feb	Science meeting
08-Feb	Jim's Hector flight - Do flight AD24 round developing convection and AE26 into anvil, with Twin Otter
09-Feb	Best Hector of the whole campaign. AD25 flew right round inflow but oil pressure transducer failed on Egrett so only Twin Otter measured anvil
10-Feb	Another superb Hector; this time we got the mission done with AD26 and AE27 plus TO/Proteus.
11-Feb	No fly today. Late Hector developed over Melville around 5.00
12-Feb	Very suppressed day. Flew AD27 south of Darwin, then AE28 (aborted) into anvil that developed in storm just SW of Darwin, with Proteus/TO
13-Feb	Suppressed again so we didn't fly Do. Storms blew up over Coburg 1230 and Tiwis 1610. Flew AE29 into Coburg storm anvil
14-Feb	Intercomparison flight: 3x60 mile dog-leg east and N of the Tiwis
15-Feb	Egrett calibration flight. End of campaign
16-Feb	Packing. Do leaves 9.00 for Bali.
17-Feb	Egrett leaves 9.00 for Adelaide

Dornier Flights

Second Campaign: Dornier flights						
	Flight	Science	Duration	Take	Land	Flight plan
		Plan	hours	off		
19-Jan	TD13	test	2.3	1234	1453	Clockwise round Tiwis at 2000' then legs at 5000'
20-Jan	AD14	MA1	3.5	14:37	1806	Transit to Cape van Diemen, eastward at 1000' to Coburg, back at 2000' then 5000' home
21-Jan						
22-Jan	AD15	MA1	2	1621	1820	Flight round storm system south of Darwin
23-Jan						
24-Jan						
25-Jan	SD16	Survey	3.5	1404	1734	Flight upwind and downwind of Tiwis with legs at 1000, 5000, 7500, 10000 and 2000
26-Jan	SD17	Survey	3	1328	1623	Flight S of Darwin with legs over coast at 5000 and 1000, then some work inland
27-Jan	SD18	Survey	3.2	1441	1752	Flight S of Darwin with legs over coast at 5000, 1000, 2000, 7500, then inland 1000,2000, 5000
28-Jan						
29-Jan						
30-Jan	SD19	Survey	4	1437	1843	Flight to measure chemical equator. Legs at 1000, 2000, 3000 and 9000' with profiles in between
31-Jan						
01-Feb	SD20	Survey	4	1008	1408	Flight to Alice Springs
02-Feb	SD21	Survey	4.4	1007	1430	Flight back from Alice Springs
03-Feb	SD22	Survey	4.3	1410	1830	Flight to measure chemical equator. Legs at 1000, 2000, 4000 and 9000' with profiles in between
04-Feb						
05-Feb						
06-Feb	AD23	MA1	3	1538	1834	Hector flight with Egrett, Proteus and Twin Otter. Flew round Hector at 1000 and 2500'
07-Feb						
08-Feb	AD24	MC1	3.6	1308	1643	Hector flight with Egrett and Twin Otter
09-Feb	AD25	MC1	3.9	1300	1650	Intended Hector flight (but Egrett failed)
10-Feb	AD26	MC1	4	1305	1705	Flight initially S of Darwin then around Hector
11-Feb						
12-Feb	AD27	MA1	3.2	1307	1618	Flight in box pattern S of Darwin. Partner to AE28
13-Feb						
14-Feb	AD28i	MI	2.8	1210	1500	Intercomparison flight: 3x60 mi dog-legs at 10, 7 and 3 kft
15-Feb						
16-Feb						
17-Feb						
Hours this campaign			54.7			
Total hours			96.65			

Dornier Equipment

Second Campaign: Dornier instrument status															
n: not flown, x: not working, p: part working, y: working															
	AIMMS	AMS	CPC	UHSAS	PSAP	ASP	Grimm	Filters	Ozone	CO	VOC	CFC	FSSP		
19-Jan	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	n	y	y	y	y	y	TD13	
20-Jan	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	AD14	
21-Jan															
22-Jan	p	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	AD15	
23-Jan															
24-Jan															
25-Jan	p	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	p	y	y	SD16	
26-Jan	p	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	SD17	
27-Jan	p	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	p	y	y	y	y	SD18	no drier on ozone unit
28-Jan															
29-Jan															
30-Jan	p	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	SD19	
31-Jan															
01-Feb	p	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	SD20	
02-Feb	p	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	n	y	SD21	
03-Feb	p	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	SD22	
04-Feb															
05-Feb															
06-Feb	p	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	AD23	
07-Feb															
08-Feb	p	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	n	y	y	AD24	
09-Feb	p	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	n	y	y	AD25	
10-Feb	p	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	n	y	y	AD26	
11-Feb															
12-Feb	p	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	n	y	y	AD27	
13-Feb															
14-Feb	p	y	y	y	y	y	y	n	y	y	y	y	y	AD28i	
p for AIMMS refers to RH which seems to be incorrectly calibrated															

EGRETT flights

Second Campaign: Egrett flights						
	Flight	Science Plan	Duration hours	Take off	Land	Flight plan
17-Jan	SE016	Transit	7.7	900	1600	Transit up from Adelaide
18-Jan						
19-Jan						
20-Jan	AE017	MA1	3.5	1505	1830	E-W runs S of Tiwis at 33000, 36000 and 40000' behind squall line
21-Jan						
22-Jan	AE018	MC1	3.2	1630	1937	Flight with Twin Otter SW from Darwin airport in anvil emanating from storm line
23-Jan	AE019	MC2	3.6	1224	1602	Flight with TO through dissipating anvil over the Timor Sea
24-Jan						
25-Jan	AE20	MA2	4	1430	1830	Flight with Proteus/TO E-W over Darwin in aged anvil plume
26-Jan						
27-Jan	AE21	MA2	4	1500	1900	Flight with Proteus/TO E-W over Darwin in aged anvil plume
31-Jan	LE22	Lidar	2.6	2022	2255	Lidar flight south of Darwin, curtailed because lidar failed
01-Feb	LE23	Lidar	3.3	2010	2330	Lidar flight south of Darwin, to 15S then east
02-Feb						
03-Feb	SE24	Survey	4	1442	1839	Survey flight to the north, with SP2
04-Feb						
05-Feb						
06-Feb	AE25	MA1	2.8	1546	1833	Hector anvil flight N of Melville, legs at 40000 and 42000'. Joint Proteus/TO
07-Feb						
08-Feb	AE26	MC1	3	1700	2000	Jim's Hector anvil flight over Bathurst, with TO
09-Feb						
10-Feb	AE27	MC1	3.75	1644	2029	Hector anvil flight over Bathurst, legs at 380, 400, 420, 440 and 380. Joint Proteus/TO
11-Feb						
12-Feb	AE28	MA1	2	1716	1916	Circumnavigation of anvil at 35000' in clear air (engine deicing failed). Joint Proteus/TO
13-Feb	AE29	MA1/2	4.2	1525	1931	Flight into anvil from storm over Cape Don area. FL 380, 410, 430, 460, 410
14-Feb	AE30i	MI	2.6	1213	1451	Intercomparison flight east and north of Melville Is.
15-Feb	TE31	Test	3.7	1215	1600	Calibration flight over Van Diemen Gulf
16-Feb						
17-Feb						
18-Feb	SE32	Transit	7.2	900	1610	Transit to Adelaide
Hours this campaign			50.25			
Hours both campaigns=			95.9			
Total so far			116.9			including transits
Assume 135 hours in total inc transits, and 7.5 hrs for last transit						
Hours left =			10.6			
Active missions			-2.35			

EGRETT Equipment

Second Campaign: Egrett instrument status

n: not flown, x: not working, p: part working, y: working

	CAPS	CDP	CPI	CO	O3	CR-2	TDL1	TDL2	VOC	GC	Met	NOX	TSI	SP2	Lidar	Flight	
17-Jan	n	n	n	n	n	n	n	y	n	x	p	n	n	n	x	SE016	Transit flight
18-Jan																	
19-Jan																	
20-Jan	x	n	y	y	y	x	y	y	y	x	p	n	p	y	n	AE017	TSI2 data not logged. Flight E-W south of squall line over Tiwis
21-Jan																	
22-Jan	y	n	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	x	y	y	y	n	n	AE018	Joint flight with TWPICE in fresh anvil S of Darwin
23-Jan	y	n	y	y		y	y	y	y	p	y	y	y	n	n	AE019	Flight with Twin Otter SW from Bathurst Is into dissipating anvil
24-Jan																	
25-Jan	y	n	x	y	y	y	y	y	p	x	y	n	y	y	n	AE20	CPI logger stopped. Joint Proteus/TO in dissipating Ci over Dwn
26-Jan																	
27-Jan	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	n	y	y	n	AE21	GC now fixed. Joint Proteus/TO in dissipating cirrus over Darwin
31-Jan	n	n	n	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	n	n	n	x	LE22	Flight to S of Darwin
01-Feb	n	n	n	y	y	y	y	y	n	y	y	n	n	n	x	LE23	Flight to S of Darwin to 15S then back along more easterly line
02-Feb																	
03-Feb	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	n	y	y	n	y	y	n	SE24	Flight NE from Darwin to monsoon trough
04-Feb																	
05-Feb																	
06-Feb	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	n	y	y	n	y	y	n	AE25	Hector, joint Proteus/TO
07-Feb																	
08-Feb	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	x	x	n	n	AE26	Hector, joint Proteus/TO
09-Feb																	
10-Feb	y	y	y	y	y	y	x	y	n	y	y	p	y	n	n	AE27	loss of att. control for last 30 min; 2.5 hr NOx data, TDL inlet taped
11-Feb																	
12-Feb	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	n	y	y	n	y	y	n	AE28	Aborted due to engine deicing failure. Flew round anvil at 35000'
13-Feb	y	y	y	y	p	y	y	y	n	y	y	n	y	y	n	AE29	Flight through anvil W of Coburg
14-Feb	y	y	n	p	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	n	y	y	n	AE30i	Intercomparison, N and W of Melville
15-Feb	y	y	y	y			y	y	n	y	y	n	y	y	n	TE31	Calibration of wind sensors
18-Feb	n	n	n	n	n	n			n			n	n	n	n	SE032	Transit flight back to Adelaide

Meteorological summary	
14-Jan	Monsoon trough extends from Gulf of C to JB Gulf. Deep W monsoon over Darwin, frequent showers
15-Jan	Strengthening NW winds with embedded showers and storms
16-Jan	Almost non-stop rain all day as the monsoon reaches its peak. Winds at 700 mb 30-35 kt
17-Jan	Very wet in the morning but rain ceased in the afternoon. Monsoon trough to the S is breaking up.
18-Jan	Monsoon trough developing into a low over WA. Focus of convection moves south
19-Jan	Low over WA has developed into TC Darryl. Squall lines to the S, quieter to the N of Darwin
20-Jan	Darryl now cat 2 but monsoon trough remains S of us. Squall lines progressing northwards during the day - AE17/AD14
21-Jan	Monsoon weakening
22-Jan	Easterly steering over Darwin. Squall line in the evening from the east
23-Jan	Low cloud at airport following passage of squall line. Cleared in the afternoon
24-Jan	Huge squall line went over during the night, turning into an MCS over the sea. Vast anvil stretching to Timor and stratiform rain all day
25-Jan	Benign conditions today despite deep WNW flow. Small inversion at 600 mb restricting showers. No ci anvils
26-Jan	All the weather to the south today, with arcs of convection coming up to Darwin. The main monsoon low continues to move southward
27-Jan	Low over central NT. Strong westerly flow producing showers over land near Darwin, reaching ~ 8 km. Deep convection over central NT
28-Jan	As yesterday, though with fewer and shallower showers. Very suppressed to the north.
29-Jan	As yesterday
30-Jan	Monsoon low moving away to WA, so winds over us abating. A few showers.
31-Jan	Low still moving slowly to WA. Fairly showery over Darwin, especially inland
01-Feb	Less showery than yesterday
02-Feb	Showers pretty well gone, except for the Tiwi Islands
03-Feb	Clear blue skies, winds abated, isolated showers over Tiwis
04-Feb	Moving to full break conditions as winds abate. Very dry air in mid-levels
05-Feb	As yesterday though with some moistening of mid-levels south of Darwin and isolated storms
06-Feb	Hector developed over North-East and central Melville. Squall line developed S of Darwin in shallow trough moving N
07-Feb	Deep convection all around Darwin with strong Hectors at 2.00 and 5.00
08-Feb	Suppressed all day until a huge Hector went off over Melville at 5.00
09-Feb	Very convective day all over the Darwin area. Massive Hectors, up to 20 km
10-Feb	Huge Hector formed over Melville, and a squall line developed to the east of Darwin
11-Feb	Big squall line in morning; large Hector developed over Melville late in the day
12-Feb	Big squall line in morning; convection developed later in the day
13-Feb	Big squall line in morning but convection developed over Coburg and Tiwis late in the day
14-Feb	Clear in the morning. Huge Hector and storms on sea breeze front E of Darwin drifting over airport
15-Feb	As yesterday